

Education Case on Deep Learning Based Electric Machine Automatic Fault Detection

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Abstract—Automatic fault detection represents a key asset in the predictive maintenance field. Unfortunately, the application of techniques based on Machine Learning (ML) is not widespread in traditional educational curricula. This paper presents a technical lecture to familiarize graduate students and predictive maintenance practitioners with Deep Learning (DL) tools for automatic fault detection. Vibration data from an open source bearing dataset is utilized for training and testing a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model. The presented content is developed in a Matlab interface, which is a widespread tool across academic institutions worldwide.

Index Terms—Training, fault diagnosis, machine learning, maintenance

I. INTRODUCTION

The electrification of several applications in many economic sectors such as automotive, energy and industry is gaining increased attention. Rotating electrical machines represent a reliable way of electromechanical energy conversion, but they are not immune to failure. The maintenance aspect of these machines represents one of the main challenges of this technology. Machine failure is critical in many applications inducing severe economic costs and jeopardizing the operation safety [1]. Traditionally, the maintenance is performed periodically or in a corrective way (i.e., once a failure evidently manifest). However, new maintenance trends are arising to overcome the lacks of these traditional approaches [2]. Predictive maintenance or condition based maintenance allows the continuous monitoring of the machinery thus, reducing the number of operations and avoiding critical on-site failure that could threaten the operation safety. The monitoring is achieved by acquiring and processing several physical quantities (e.g., vibrations, temperature, phase current, etc.) by using suitable tools. Nowadays, a vast amount of academic and industrial research effort is focused on this topic [3].

Faults in rotating electric machines mainly occur in the stator winding and bearings, where the latter represents approximately the 44% of the total failures [4]. The utilization of vibration data to detect and address bearing faults is broadly

accepted in industry [5] and attracts constant research attention from both academia and industrial actors [6]. The categorization of such faults provides useful information regarding the origin and possible mitigation mechanisms of the bearing defect. Several works can be found in literature where the faults are categorized following different quantitative criteria (i.e., defining characteristic frequencies for each type of fault) [7], [8]. One of the current technical challenges is related to the automatic detection and classification of bearing faults. To this aim, several researchers utilize novel tools based on Machine Learning (ML). A comprehensive study about ML techniques for electric machine fault diagnosis and prognosis is found in [9]. Deep Learning (DL) techniques represent the final abstraction of ML [10]. These type of methods allow the automatic fault feature extraction. One of the most common DL techniques is based on signal-to-image transformation and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) usage. Wen et al. [11] present a novel methodology to convert vibration data into images (i.e., signal-to-image conversion) and to automatically detect faults by utilizing a CNN. The authors prove the superiority of this technique over traditional ML methods.

The education on Artificial Intelligence (AI), ML and particularly, DL represents an asset for predictive maintenance future practitioners. Works on electric machinery maintenance education are found in literature, where the authors highlight the presence of maintenance education in different engineering degrees [12]. The inclusion of ML-based techniques on predictive maintenance courses is of capital importance, particularly to identify bearing faults via vibration signals. To this aim, this work introduces a technical lecture that was conceived to illustrate new ML users on the main advantages of such techniques. The presented content can be utilized as a traditional lecture as well as a hands-on tutorial. A Matlab interface is utilized due to the widespread application across academia institutions. Section II describes the education context for the lecture, Section III presents the main technical content and Section IV concludes the work.

II. EDUCATION CONTEXT

The integration of AI techniques in several sectors triggers the attention of several funding institutions. This is the case of the DITARTIS project (i.e., Network of Excellence in

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Fig. 1. Base work-flow of the proposed methodology

Digital Technologies and AI Solutions for Electromechanical and Power Systems Applications), an European Commission founded twinning project involving several institutions from different European countries. A set of different training events to be held in a hybrid manner are defined in the proposal and implemented across the project.

The first training event was mainly aimed to provide to the research community and graduate level students with basic knowledge on AI tools. Table I presents an outline of the presented courses. In addition, two lectures were aimed to the application of AI tools in predictive maintenance (i.e., lectures 5 and 6 in Table I).

TABLE I
TRAINING EVENT LECTURES

1	AI: Challenges and opportunities for electromechanical and power systems applications
2	AI: Theory and applications in Computer-Aided Engineering
3	From Artificial Intelligence to Deep Learning
4	AI tools for energy flexibility (PV forecasting, aggregation, optimization, and trading based on Big Data, IoT, Machine learning/AI, and blockchain)
5	Application of machine learning techniques to predict intermittent earth fault in MV distribution networks
6	Deep Learning tools for automatic diagnosis of rotating electrical machines via vibration signals

A different aim for the presented lecture is to serve as hands-on lecture or workshop for predictive maintenance practitioners or graduate level students. The utilization of digital tools and absence of physical test enables the teaching both in on-line and on-site modalities.

III. TECHNICAL DESCRIPTIONS

The present section describes the technical content presented during the lecture and poses the main technical challenges. The ideal scenario in the industry is the accurate fault detection of the target machinery in an on-line mode and with a high degree of accuracy. The first step is to acquire the objective signals (i.e., in this case vibration data) by utilizing dedicated sensors and analogue/digital signal converters. These signals are then input in a dedicated control architecture that executes the data processing and automatic fault detection, which is performed by a pre-trained architecture. An off-line process is required to generate the pre-trained CNN model. This paper mainly focuses on the off-line work flow that generates the automatic detection network (i.e., the CNN). Figure 1 shows a block diagram with the main steps of the presented approach.

Open source data sets represent a valid alternative to generate pre-trained architectures for automatic fault detection. The

bearing vibration data from Paderborn University's Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, is utilized for this case study [13]. This dataset presents several synchronously measured motor currents and vibration signals of 26 damaged bearing states and 6 healthy states. In addition, the shaft speed and torque, radial load, and temperature are also acquired. For each signal 20 measurements of 4 seconds per-setting are performed. These characteristics represent a feasible framework for CNN model training.

A. Data acquisition and presentation

The utilized dataset includes data of several bearing damages including artificially induced damages (e.g., drills, trenches, etc.) and damages generated by accelerated lifetime tests. This work only includes the artificially induced fault detection since the damages are more comprehensive to the non-expert practitioner. The dataset is generated in the test bench described in figure 2. The faulty bearings are inserted in a measurement module, where vibration in radial direction and temperature are monitored. In addition, the module allows the application of radial force in the bearing. The dataset also includes phase current data measured in two phases of the main motor. The torque meter provides the speed and average torque values.

The different artificially damaged bearings are tested under different operating regimes. These include different speed, torque, and applied radial force values. For each operating point, 20 measurements of 4 seconds each are performed. The signals are acquired with a sampling rate of 64 kHz. The dataset contains .mat files containing all the acquired data and properly labelled. The labels contain information about speed, torque, radial force, bearing code, and number of measurement (i.e., numbers ranging from 1 to 20). The bearing code for artificially induced damages is shown in Table II, where EDM

Fig. 2. Data acquisition test bench, reconstruction from [13]

Fig. 3. Signal-to-image process of the proposed methodology

TABLE II
BEARING CODES FOR ARTIFICIAL DAMAGE

Bearing Code	Location of fault	Severity (level 1 or 2)	Method
KA01	Outer Race	1	EDM
KA03	Outer Race	2	engraver perforation
KA05	Outer Race	1	engraver perforation
KA06	Outer Race	2	engraver perforation
KA07	Outer Race	1	drilling
KA08	Outer Race	2	drilling
KA09	Outer Race	2	drilling
KI01	Inner Race	1	EDM
KI03	Inner Race	1	engraver perforation
KI05	Inner Race	1	engraver perforation
KI07	Inner Race	2	engraver perforation
KI08	Inner Race	2	engraver perforation

stands for Electric Discharge Machining. More information about artificial defect implementation is available in [13]

B. Data processing and image generation

The educational approach of the work requires a simple and comprehensive signal-to-image method. In addition, it should perform well for the automatic detection task and needs to store the images as efficiently as possible. The adopted approach is based on spectrogram generation via Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and the further image processing by reducing its size and transforming it into a greyscale version. Figure 3 shows the proposed signal-to-image process.

The first step is to read the raw vibration data. It is important to highlight the importance of the sampling frequency of the signal, in this case $f_s = 64$ kHz, since it heavily influences the resolution of the STFT. The raw signal can be downsampled prior to the STFT application to control the frequency resolution. The STFT is analytically defined as follows:

$$X(\tau, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)g(t - \tau)e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad (1)$$

where τ represents a discrete time window, ω represents the pulsation and $g(t - \tau)$ is a sliding window function that depends on the difference between the instantaneous time and the considered time window. In simple words, the STFT

performs the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of single discrete time windows defined by the user. To implement the STFT in a Matlab environment the simple *spectrogram* function is utilized, where the window length (i.e., τ) and the overlap between windows represent two degrees of freedom adjusted by the user. In addition, the type of window to be utilized in the single window FFTs in input. The recommended option to avoid excessive spectral leakage is to utilize a Hanning window.

The next step is to standardize the image size. This is heavily defined by the CNN input even if the size is a user tunable parameter. In addition, the size influences the storage space occupied by the single images, which can be excessive when the amount of data is large. The size should be even in x- and y-directions for the application at hand. Thus, the selected size is 224x224 pixels. The images are converted into greyscale to reduce the number of image channels, which heavily influences the occupied storage space (i.e., from three channels in RGB to a single channel of the greyscale). Finally, these images are automatically stored in folders defined by the user.

C. Data clustering strategy

The generated greyscale images are stored in folders named after the bearing codes presented in Table II and the healthy states. Then, the data is separated into training and test groups. The training data is utilized to train the CNN model, while the test data serves as performance evaluation of the trained classifier. It's important to highlight in an education context the different ways the data is split prior to the training. The clustering and separation of the data is automatically performed by a Matlab script, where the input parameters are the percentages of training and test data.

D. CNN architecture definition

The understanding of DL basics is normally burdensome to the non-expert users. The Deep Network Designer of Matlab is utilized in this work, which includes a Guided User Interface (GUI) that eases the CNN model generation and training. Moreover, the application includes several pre-trained models

Fig. 4. GoogleNet architecture and details from Matlab GUI

for automatic image recognition that could serve as example for the application at hand.

The CNN represents a variation of classical fully connected neural networks. Inspired by the working principle of the visual cortex, a sliding window of few pixels length and identifying particular features swipes the whole image. After evaluating the whole image by a set of different features only the highest scored areas are selected, which is known as max pooling. After several stages of convolutions and max pooling, the output is fed to a fully connected network where the final fault classification is performed. Further information about the CNN working principle is available in [10] as well as in a large amount of on-line resources.

For educational purposes, a pre-trained CNN model is selected for this work. The GoogleNet architecture [14] is selected since it is easily available on-line as well as in the Matlab application. Figure 4 presents the whole view of the architecture with details about the initial, inception and fully connected layers. Figure 4 (a) shows the initial section of the architecture where the image input layer is tuned to process 224x224 images. The inception section (i.e., figure 4 (b)) includes four parallel branches in parallel, which enables the multi scaling processing of the images. This is the main advantage of the GoogleNet architecture. Figure 4 (c) shows the fully connected layer and the classifier of the architecture. Further information about the CNN architecture can be found in [14].

E. Training Process

The training data represents the 50% of the whole dataset for the presented example. The 70 % is utilized for training and 30% for validation. In this stage it is important to highlight the meaning of several concepts regarding neural network training. The batch term is still ambiguous up to this date. A batch

is normally referred to the number of training samples in a forward-backward pass. However, some users understand that a batch includes the whole training set. To solve the issue, the forward-backward data pass is commonly named as mini-batch. A single iteration is referred as a mini-batch pass. Finally, the term epoch is defined to describe the number of times the whole algorithm processes the entire data set. The CNN training process achieved a 94.5 % of accuracy in 41 epochs and 400 iterations. The total training time is approximately 4 hours 24 minutes.

F. Model test

The testing stage is aimed to provide information about the accuracy of the trained model predictions. A common methodology to perform the model test is to build confusion matrices. The confusion matrix relates the predicted classes with the real class of each signal. In this way, the more percentage of results falls within the diagonal of the matrix, the more accurate the CNN model is. The elements in the off-diagonal terms correspond to the model incorrect predictions. Figure 5 shows the confusion matrix generated for the trained CNN, with a data s of 50% training data and 50 % test data. The labels *IR* and *OR* refer to inner race and outer race bearing fault respectively.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This article presents a technical lecture on DL techniques applied to the predictive maintenance field for rotating electrical machines. The application of such techniques represents an asset for both industrial practitioners and academia researchers. The main objective of the lecture is to introduce graduate level students and maintenance practitioners with novel DL techniques in a simple and intuitive manner. The utilized data is available on-line as an open-source resource

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix of the trained CNN, 50% test data

[13]. The method is based on a work-flow including data acquisition, signal-to-image processing, CNN model architecture definition, training, and testing. This technical content allows several educational formats such as classical lecture or hands on tutorial. In addition, it is easily adaptable to on-site, on-line or hybrid attendance. Future work will be focused on the Matlab script adaptation for a more hands on format, where the tunable parameters of each Matlab script are property highlighted and described. Moreover, the inclusion of the content in official predictive maintenance academic curricula will be evaluated.

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